

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 1 of 16

**EXPLORING THE IN-PERSON TO ONLINE, FLEXIBLE TEACHING AND BACK:
FROM THE LENS OF NURSE EDUCATORS' AND SELF-EFFICACY ON ONLINE
TEACHING: TOWARDS A FUNCTIONAL TRAINING PROGRAM**

**Marissa lyn A. Labangcoc, RN, MSN, Mary Rose C. Jontilano, RN, MSN, Thelma D. Delos Reyes, RN, RM, MSN,
Mary Antoinette B. Aseron, RN, MSN, and Peter-Tom A. Callang, RN, MAN**

Abstract

For educators and schools all over the world, transitioning to online education during the Covid-19 presented difficulties. To assess online teaching self-efficacy (TSE) during COVID-19 and investigate participants' experiences during the transition from face-to-face teaching to online and back, this study used a mixed-method design. Seven of the 20 participants were contacted for an in-depth interview to explore their experiences during the transition. Results using the MNESEOT obtained scores of $M=15.93$, $SD=2.19$, which implies a moderate online teaching efficacy. Initial uncertainties, Issues caused by the disconnection with the students, managing situations, a good changeover, and lessons learned emerged as themes in the nurse educator's transition. Proposed activities are training on instructional materials development and use of technology. Regardless of the teaching mode, they will undergo transition. This study shows the benefit of educating and training nurse faculty to increase their self-efficacy as teachers. When there is a crisis in the educational system, nurse educators can adjust by having access to programs for faculty development that are tailored to their needs.

Key words: Nursing, COVID-19, Nursing Education, Teaching Efficacy

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in several adjustments to the educational system. In the nursing profession, in particular, modifications to the nursing curriculum are necessary to increase the use of high-fidelity simulation to assist students in completing their mandatory clinical rotations (Redden, 2020). But even with the latest technology, the use of online modes in education and learning has challenged everyone.

The most recent and widely used form of education today is online distance learning. It was introduced decades earlier, the first completely online course was conducted in 1984 by the University of Toronto (Sarkar, 2020). It has grown in popularity since then, and its use exploded in 2020 when universities and offices were forced to close indefinitely as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Online learning was critical in facilitating students' learning during the shutdown of universities and schools (Subedi et al., 2020). Teachers must be prepared for every circumstance, especially when using internet tools to instruct. This is possible when educators also learn to develop their self-efficacy in online teaching to the new adjustment.

The concept of self-efficacy was first introduced by Bandura in his social-cognitive paradigm of behavioral change (Bandura, 1977). It is the belief a teacher has in his or her ability to successfully handle the duties, responsibilities, and difficulties connected to his or her professional role (Caprara et al., 2006). Several researchers had brought attention to the COVID-19 pandemic to study the online teaching self-efficacy (TSE) among educators across educational levels and in nursing, in particular. Studies reveal the self-efficacy of online instruction was highly perceived (Baroudi and Shaya (2022), Culp-Roche et al. (2021). Baroudi and Shaya further reveal that teachers with

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 2 of 16

prior online teaching experience excelled over those with little or no experience in terms of self-efficacy. While studies report a higher online teaching self-efficacy the study by Atout et al. (2022), presented the challenges concerning clinical courses including a lack of resources, a lack of interaction, evaluation, and their home environment. Meanwhile, Moradi et al (2022), participants identified "inappropriate groundwork" and "low inclination to virtual education" as the main challenges of the sudden shift to asynchronous e-learning in nursing education during the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, teachers must be prepared for each situation by teaching using online applications.

On the other hand, along with the pandemic, the sudden shift to the online modality had brought attention to exploring the educators' experiences. It is because the transition from face-to-face to online teaching may be a completely new experience for both learners and educators (Pokhrel and Chhetri, 2021). The transitions that the nurse educators experienced in this study were analyzed based on the Schlossberg Theory. Which states that a transition is "any event or non-event that leads in changing relationships, routines, assumptions, and roles," according to Schlossberg et al(1995). This can be reflected in the transitions of nurse educators in their teaching in this study. Studies about transitions had emerged which include the challenges and struggles during the shift to online teaching modality. Wilson et al. (2021) reveal the transition of nursing faculty, they were resourceful, adaptable, and eager to employ both new and established resources and approaches to achieve their teaching goals and engage students. Additionally, they were generally happy with the administrative assistance they got from their particular institutions. As more programs and courses are likely to continue being managed online, many of these tools, techniques, and supports will likely still be employed by teachers.

With the control of the COVID-19 pandemic, another modality was introduced, which is flexible learning. The term flexible learning describes the blending of several instructional modalities, such as the usage of online platforms and digital or printed modules. Universities and colleges used a variety of alternative teaching and learning approaches under this new structure, depending on their unique circumstances (Rojas, 2021). The article by Martin and Uliana (2020) presented the Education 2030 Agenda and Sustainable Development Goal 4 recognized the need for flexible higher education systems to provide diverse learning pathways to support equity and lifelong learning even before the COVID-19 crisis. It further highlighted that by combining face-to-face provision with elements of distance and online learning, higher education institutions can be better equipped to provide flexible learning pathways to a variety of students. According to the findings of Muller and Steingruber (2023) when implementing flexible study programs in a blended learning design, special attention should be paid to the following educational design principles: sufficient course structure and guidance for students, activating learning tasks, stimulating interaction and social presence of teachers, and timely feedback on learning process and outcomes. This could mean that while flexible learning is identified as an alternative modality in teaching during the pandemic, it is a must that each has enough preparation for the implementation of the modality.

With flexible learning, another transition was expected among the nurse educators which could mean the need to deal with changes from pure online distance learning. Garcia and Cruz's (2022) study reveals course participants had to deal with issues such as limited technology availability, instructor and student unpreparedness, cultural prejudice against online or remote learning, and economic considerations. On the other hand, switching to this form of delivery is thought to have advantages such as fresh perspectives and abilities for teachers, opportunities for students to learn independently, access to learning resources, and increased resilience for educational institutions.

Then finally, after 2 years as the COVID-19 pandemic had shown gradual resolution worldwide. The Philippine schools have started to reopen their campuses to students as the Covid-19 outbreak begins to fade Carpena (2022). The article further presents that although each goes back to face-to-face, one should consider the use of technologies to help improve the learning and teaching processes even in face-to-face classes. Many people see this as a return to normal. This implies another transition to take place among educators. However, in-person instruction

SAINT MARY' S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 3 of 16

during the COVID-19 pandemic has made teachers anxious, Wakui et al. (2021) further reiterate that knowing the causes of educational worry and infection-related concerns that teachers encounter in face-to-face sessions during a pandemic, the report offers helpful information. This could mean that the transition had challenged again all people, just like during the gradual shift to online.

Despite the many studies exploring the experience of transition from face-to-face teaching to online, a lack of studies was noted on exploring the experience along the following transition scenarios, online teaching to flexible learning and back to face-to-face teaching modality among nurse educators in particular. Which is the main scope of the current study. Documentation of significant experiences during the transitions could contribute to the nursing education, if a crisis in the educational system again strikes, noting the experience had already prepared us, a lesson learned for a lifetime. The study also looked into the proposed activities for faculty development relevant to the improvement of teaching online. Burns (2016) states that for instructors to participate in online courses, they must first have access to the most basic infrastructures, use of the internet, and learning resources like textbooks and course materials. Additionally, Baroudi and Shaya identified important factors like getting support for developing online instruction and getting professional development in online teaching. Bisnar (2022) also suggested that teachers must be able to keep up with technological changes to properly prepare students in a digital age. Therefore, schools must ensure then that teachers receive consistent, continuous training and skill development that ensures efficacy in teaching in various modes of modalities.

Given this, the study was conducted to investigate the online teaching self-efficacy of nurse educators and explore the experience of transition who switched from face-to-face to online instruction, to flexible learning and back to face-to-face teaching, including the proposed activities to enhance their teaching. The fight against the COVID-19 pandemic is still ongoing and possible crisis may affect us again in the future. It is important then to determine the nurse educators' self-efficacy in online teaching and look into their experiences with it. The findings of this study may help nurse educators gain insight into their self-efficacy in teaching online as they move forward with future attempts to employ the online modality in addition to face-to-face instruction toward a functional training program.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the perceived level of self-efficacy on online teaching and the lived experiences of nurse educators' transitions during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, it will seek to address the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of self-efficacy of the nurse educators on online teaching in terms of.
 - 1.1 student engagement
 - 1.2 instructional strategies
 - 1.3 online classroom management
 - 1.4 use of computer
2. To describe the pattern and meaning of the experience for the nurse educators' transition from face-to-face to online to flexible learning and back.
3. To determine the proposed activities to enhance the nurse educator's self-efficacy in online teaching.

SAINT MARY' S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 4 of 16

Methodology

A retrospective survey using a mixed-method approach was employed in the study. The level of self-efficacy in online teaching was described by the researchers using a descriptive quantitative approach, and the lived experiences of nurse educators in the transition were explored which improves the reliability of the findings. The study was conducted in a selected tertiary institution offering the nursing program, the school had to make the sudden transition from traditional face-to-face to online teaching to flexible learning and back. Initially, the school utilized a virtual learning modality. But in the latter due to the unprecedented event of the COVID-19 outbreak, work from home was done for the school year (2020-2021), then followed by a transition to limited face-to-face or flexible learning by S.Y. 2021-2022 then back to face-to-face teaching by S.Y. 2022-2023.

The participants are the nurse educators who have transitioned to at least 1 face-to-face teaching and taught professional nursing subjects in online classes during the COVID-19 pandemic and are currently teaching during the academic year 2022-2023, teaching either lecture or related learning experience (RLE) professional nursing subjects and are willing to participate. The researchers utilized a purposive sampling technique using the inclusion criteria in choosing the respondents. There are 20 respondents, who answered the survey and open-ended questions. While seven (7) respondents were purposively interviewed considering the full-time faculty and with a full load of 24 units during the transition.

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 5 of 16

Description of the Respondents

Table 1 Profile of the respondents

	Profile of Respondents	Frequency	Percent
Age	35-45	9	45
	46-55	7	35
	56-greater	4	20
	Total	20	100.0
Gender	Male	4	20
	Female	16	80
	Total	20	100.0
Highest Educational Attainment	Bachelor	1	5
	Masterate	17	85
	Doctorate	2	10
	Total	20	100.0
Years of Teaching	1-10	1	10
	11-20	18	85
	21-30	1	5
	Total	20	100.0
Years of Teaching Online	1	8	40
	2	12	60
	Total	20	100.0
Attended Online Webinar	No	4	20
	Yes	16	80
Number of Online Webinars Attended	0-3	14	70
	4-7	5	25
	8-10	1	5
	Total	20	100

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 6 of 16

The study participants were 20 faculty members; the majority are female (16) most between the ages of 35 to 45 years. The participants' years of experience ranged from 11 to 20 years, seventeen with master's degrees. Sixteen participants attended online webinars while four of them did not attend any training.

The study utilized an adapted instrument from the study of Culp-Roche's (2021), MNESEOT (Michigan Nurse Educators Sense of Efficacy for Online Teaching). A 32 item scale was used to assess the effectiveness of online instruction.

Participants responded to each question with a response ranging from (1) "None at all" to (9) "A Great Deal," indicating how they felt about it. The more points added together, the more effective that part of online education is felt to be. All of the instrument's items were used, but the researchers decided to change the response options to a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 being the lowest response and 5 being the highest. To make it simple to respond to the questions, the options were revised. Participants were required to respond to a total of 5 semi-structured open-ended questions as part of the qualitative instrument.

The study was conducted face-to-face, secured first the informed consent, their signatures affixed to the form. The researchers used the questionnaire on self-efficacy and initially asked the respondents to answer the questionnaire and guide questions in the written format during the survey. A scheduled interview was done after, using the same guide questions to further validate the answers of the respondents. Participants' answers or responses to the guide questions were videos recorded with the consent of the respondents. Several very important points were also noted, especially the observed non-verbally of the interviewees, with 1-2 of the researchers in attendance at all of the interviews.

The data to be collected in this study will be subjected to the following statistical treatment. The study will make use of descriptive statistics, frequency count, and distribution to describe the profile. Mean, median, and standard deviation to present the perceived online teaching self-efficacy. The researchers will make use of thematic analysis; this type of analysis comprises reading through a set of data, thus identifying patterns and meanings across data.

The researchers belong to the study population but do not belong to the respondent. The researchers are also excluded from the study although they belong to the target population, as they could influence the result of the study. Furthermore, as part of the study population, researchers can ensure, and not compromise the integrity of gathered data and study results by strictly maintaining the authenticity of each respondent's answer, and by maintaining a research-respondent relationship. Furthermore, to preserve the participants' privacy, confidentiality, and comfort, every ethical concern relevant to the study was taken into account. For those who agreed to engage in the study, the participants provided the researchers with both written and verbal informed consent before the study began. The freedom to leave the study at any moment was granted to the participants. All documents and study materials were properly secured.

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 7 of 16

RESULTS

Sense of Self-Efficacy in Online Teaching

Table 3 Total MNESEOT SCORES

Total MNESEOT Score (N=20)	Mean	SD	Range
Student Engagement	4.025	.654	1-5
Instructional Practices	4.113	.473	1-5
Classroom Management	3.975	.665	1-5
Use of Computers	3.812	.617	1-5
Total MNESEOT Score	15.93	2.197	4-20

Legend: 1.00-1.49 Nothing 3.50-4.49 Quite A Bit
 1.50-2.49 Very Little 4.50-5.00 A Great Deal
 2.50-3.49 Some

The table above presents 32 items from the survey. Participants' average response on a scale from 0 to 20 was 15.93, with a standard deviation of 2.19. Overall, the nurse educators who answered the questionnaire felt they could do "quite a bit" in terms of facilitating student engagement, classroom management, use of instructional practices, and computers.

The majority of the respondents 17 (85%) reported 11-20 years of face-to-face teaching experience (n=20). This degree of experience does contribute to the effectiveness of online instruction. In terms of nurse educators indicating they felt they could do "quite a bit" in online instruction, the survey sample's overall mean of MNESEOT scores (M=15.93, SD=2.19) implies a moderate online teaching efficacy score.

Experience on the transition

Several themes emerged from the twenty (20) participants who answered the open-ended questions and the seven (7) participants who were purposefully chosen for the interview about their experiences switching from in-person instruction to online instruction and back again (Table 4).

Table 4 Emerging themes about the experience in the transition

Themes	Exemplary
Problems on use of technology (n=20)	"There is a need to learn the system (LMS-ESMIS) along with brownouts/no signal or internet connection.
Lack of student engagement (n=10)	"I had a difficulty to motivate the students to participate in the discussion"
Burden on Workload (n=11)	"Online teaching demands great effort and lots of time and preparation."
Innovations of teaching strategies(n=9)	"I had to adapt my teaching strategies"

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 8 of 16

Table 5 Description of Interviewees

Pseudonyms	Age	Experience (Years)	Educational Attainment	Online TSE Total Score (20)
Tom	52	20	Masterate	11.25
Jane	35	12	Masterate	15.36
Mary	45	9	Masterate	17.88
Rina	49	9	Bachelor	19.38
Tina	36	16	Masterate	14
John	39	18	Doctorate	14.63
Ana	40	16	Masterate	17

Face-to-Face to Online Transition to Flexible Learning and Back

Theme 1 Initial uncertainties

All interviewees (n = 7) initially felt difficulty and were challenged by the new experience from the transition, from face-to-face teaching to online teaching, feeling overwhelmed in embracing the new modality of teaching with the sudden school lockdown during the pandemic. The concerns were raised, in terms of what they felt initially when there was a sudden shift to online. One participant said, initially "It was a little bit shocking during that time" (Tom). Which could be an initial reaction every time someone encounters a sudden change to usual activities. Identified concerns include a lack of knowledge of the new platform of teaching, although the majority have moderate self-efficacy in online teaching. There is also a need to adapt to new teaching strategies applicable to the virtual classroom. Several concerns were raised on technical problems, such as the use of the internet, gadgets, and others. A statement a participant says: "... it was very challenging kasi you need to address so many issues such technical, logistical issues, so we can ensure students have access to internet (John).

One participant similarly added: "I had a hard time. You need to have a lot of readings and training on how to conduct online class".(Rina)

However, it is good to note that, there is a gradual improvement in the teaching and learning process, such as the usage of a new platform, development of learning materials such as power point presentations and videos, use of online applications learned during the conduct of training and adjustment process on how to conduct online teaching. A participant said:At first siyempre mahirap, kasi we don't know how to start, ung internet connection, gadget, paano magkakaroon ng mga conferences, uploading, paggawa natin ng mga videos. Ung pag-transition starts from easy, moderate, saka difficult. (Jane)

Theme 2 Issues caused by the disconnection with the students

In the transition period during online teaching, several issues were identified using the modality, that had challenged each participant.

SAINT MARY' S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 9 of 16

The participants (n = 6) reveal that online teaching disconnected them from their students, due to this it caused difficulty in monitoring the student's performance, especially during the RLE (Related Learning Experience) in the virtual classroom, addressing misconduct, and providing timely feedback. The participants could not see the students and in some instances, they had to mute the students online to control their noise. In some instances, students were reported to leave their account active while they were sleeping or even playing computer games or doing household chores.

For instance, Ana who worked as both lecturer and RLE Instructor claimed that she was disgusted because nobody would respond to her random calls for recitation as she said: *"pag mag co-call ka na ng names wala nang sumasagot, parang wala nang nakikinig."* (Ana). Another instance in the class of Tonie where one of her students would fake his presence by putting a shirt onto a chair that would look like someone is seated on that chair listening to the lecture. She would say, *nakainis, but what can I do? I cannot hold them physically. I have to do another scheme in able to engage them to stay and listen, nakakinit talaga ng ulo."* (Tonie).

The follow-up of students whether they learned or not also emerged as one issue to address during the online teaching transition. One of the respondents admitted, *"nakaka bother yung pag- follow up ng students if they understood the instructions in their activities. Nasundan kaya nila? (Rina)*

The researchers significantly noted also the participants questioning their delivery of lessons. One bluntly stated: There are questions at times, am I delivering good or worst, kasi you cannot see their actual responses unlike in the classroom. *Am I satisfactorily delivering the lessons? (Tom)*

Theme 3 Managing Difficult Situations

The participants (n = 5) reported that despite all the difficulties, they were able to manage themselves in the transition period. The transition journey reflected a gradual transition. To a certain extent, the participants managed the transition period through self-directed learning. As they get used to the new modality, they learn to innovate and adapt to new strategies and techniques in teaching. Aside from the recognition of various support from others.

Tina reported, *nag ask din ako ng help from other instructors na nakapag experience na. Pero more on accidentally ko lang, sarili kong natutunan yung LMS.* She further added, *accidental or trial and error ko lang nadidiscovers kung paano gagawin. (Tina)* Another statement is: *Noon, ang nakatulong sa akin ay ung support from the family kasi kelangan na mag work ka. Number 2 is ay ung camaraderie ng SHANS nursing faculty. Malaking tulong din ang sa management ng Saint Mary's University, we have seminars noon. (Jane)*

Theme 4 A good changeover

The nurse educators' gradual transition from purely online to flexible learning and then face-to-face teaching modality most especially in the RLE gave each participant a good transition, though recognized as another adjustment. However, it is good to note that the transition was smooth and that some mentioned did not transition at all, it was like going back to the usual routines of teaching. One participant, happily states:

Sa flexible hindi ako nahirapan, although syempre nanibago. Pero pagdating sa lecture, hindi ka masyadong mag adjust. Ung transition ko diyan mas ng enjoy ako, mas naging exciting ang pagtuturo. (Jane) Similarly, another participant appreciated the flexible teaching modality. *Yung online to mix, mas madali, mas maganda ung flexible dahil meron pa rin covid. With the transition, I was excited, halos wala ng difficulty kasi, the lecture classroom management is better. (Tom)*

Though, it was also noted that flexible teaching is far better than pure online several concerns were also identified. With the current situation of COVID-19, the need to strictly follow the minimum health protocol had challenged all during the transition. With the observance of the limited face-to-face guidelines, such as the use of PPE in full attire,

SAINT MARY' S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 10 of 16

the hot environment is somehow regarded as a barrier to teaching. *Yung isang challenge nung face-to-face na. Yung kelangan I implement yung mga new health protocols to prevent the spread of COVID-19. (John)*

There are also disadvantages identified in the flexible teaching, the majority of the participants strongly agree with the flexible modality as an option to continuously adapt to the new trend of teaching using technology. The online modality was embraced by the nurse educators and needs development activities in the technological world, the efforts to adjust, adapt and learn the modality should not be taken aside. One participant stated: Limited to face-to-face, mas madali, mas mabilis yun adjustment, kasi you are just going back to the previous practice na (Mary).

Then finally, at last looking forward to going back to the classroom once again as the Covid-19 cases declined. Schools begin to re-open for face-to-face classes. The transition from flexible teaching to face-to-face was another remarkable transition, each participant after some difficulties in online teaching, then to flexible learning, going back to full face-to-face as another important transition.

Masaya ako, kasi hands on na ang clinical experiences, which we know are critical for nursing education. Na miss ko din yung in-person instruction mas naka ka-communicate din with iinteraction between students and the faculty. (John)

From flexible learning to face-to-face, a better transition and seems a relief from all the uncertainties experienced during the online transition. A participant state:

The transition from flexible learning to face-to-face is less stressful or a good transition because I'm used to face to face teaching (Tina)

Theme 5 Lessons Learned

With the entire transition in teaching online, to flexible, and then going back to face-to-face, the changes brought a stronger outlook in life among the nurse educators, whether the experience was positive or negative. It was an opportunity to continuously ignite each nurse educator's commitment to their call, to teach the next generations of nurses despite struggles and difficulties in life. The participants (n=5) claim that despite difficulties and struggles in the transition, they see it as a great learning experience and an opportunity to continuously hone their teaching skills. Among the responses include: *The experience, is a new learning. My realization, is learn more and explore and be better as a teacher. (Tom)* Another respondent said *"Lahat ng nangyari from pandemic ni ready tayo. Lalo na sa nursing career natin parang mas nagiging challenging. Sa lahat ng challenges na encounter natin mas nagiging stronger ka na instructor (Jane).*

Proposed faculty Development Activities

Table 6 Proposed Faculty Development Activities

Activities (n=20)	f	%
Instructional Materials Development Use of	12	60
Technology in teaching	11	55
Online Instructional strategies	4	20

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 11 of 16

Table 6 reveals the proposed faculty development activities of the participants, twelve(60%) proposed having activities in terms of instructional materials development enhanced by technology. Followed by the use of technology, eleven (55%) and four (20%) on online instructional modalities

Discussions

The Online Teaching Self-Efficacy (TSE) among nurse educators during the COVID-19 school lockdown is determined by this study. The study's overall findings show that TSE is moderate. On the contrary the study of Hampton et al (2020), and Culp-Roche et al. (2021), results showed relatively high levels of online teaching self-efficacy. Self-efficacy in teaching may be affected by several factors, In the case of the study participants, it could be because everybody had to adapt to the new online teaching modality for the first time. But a moderate self-efficacy could have resulted in their gradual transition of teaching.

Being one of the few studies undertaken in the setting of online teaching during a pandemic among nurse educators who switched from face-to-face to online, flexible education and back is a significant strength of these findings. A key fact from the findings of the study was average online teaching self-efficacy after online teaching despite a new experience in the online teaching modality. It is noted that the majority of the respondents are seasoned nurse educators which could have contributed to their level of self-efficacy, able to gradually adapt and cope with difficulties. Seasoned teachers cope by using appropriate communication and understanding of their classroom's circumstances (Santos, 2021).

On the other hand, the online teaching transition took place for more than 2 years, which could imply a gradual exposure to the online modality, eventually learning the skill and the self-efficacy for technology applications improved significantly over time, which supports the finding (Lee and Tsai, 2010) that indicates TSE for technology applications increases with increases in online teaching experience. In the analysis of the transition of nurse educators in teaching during the pandemic, 5 themes emerged in the interview. First is the initial uncertainty encountered at the beginning of the transition. Being uncertain every time we encounter new experiences is unavoidable, such as the use of a new modality among nurse educators. Uncertainty may range from a falling short of certainty to an almost complete lack of conviction or knowledge especially about an outcome or result. The predominant stressors were uncertainty about the consequences of the pandemic, work overload, and inadequate working environment (Vargas and Oros, 2021).

The second theme presents the issues caused by the disconnection with the students. Being disconnected from the students due to online distance learning is one of the identified significant transitions the participants had to address. The situation holds strongly in a study wherein the researcher discovered similar problems of online learning like distractions, frustration, anxiety & confusion, and lack of personal/physical attention (Dhawan and Shivangi, 2020). A survey study that was conducted earlier supports this particular concern of student disconnection, wherein it found that online learning lacks a sense of community (Song, L., Singleton, E. S., Hill, J. R., & Koh, M. H., 2004). In addition, having trouble staying motivated was the issue that responders to the survey most frequently mentioned. When students discussed their motivational struggles, they emphasized losing their daily routine, having conflicting priorities, and just feeling disconnected from their teachers and fellow students (Hinton, 2020). In a teaching and learning process, a special bond or connection between the teacher and learners has to be established. Their thoughts must be aligned, and the interest of both teachers and learners in the topics has to be maintained. Online teaching is a powerful instrument considering its flexibility in time, and space and its applicability to a large number of audiences, however, the

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 12 of 16

establishment and maintenance of the connection with the students greatly rests on the ability of the teacher to catch their attention and hold them for a specified period.

Managing difficult situations emerged during the transition. Each was able to continue to teach despite encountering challenges and struggles in teaching. According to Wilson et al. (2021) regarding the transition of nursing faculty, they were resourceful, adaptable, and eager to employ both new and established resources and approaches to achieve their teaching goals and engage students. Additionally, they were generally happy with the administrative assistance they got from their particular institutions. While Firmansyah and Bandonno (2022) state teachers must be innovative and imaginative while creating lesson plans. Expected improvements include those in methodologies, media, and learning environments so they can continue to teach despite any obstacles.

After the difficulties encountered in the transition online, a good changeover was noted in the flexible learning and back to face-to-face transition of teaching. Which means that there was a good transition. Although, concerns in the transition include the anxiety felt going out due to the pandemic. In-person instruction during the COVID-19 pandemic has made teachers anxious, according to Wakui et al. (2021) further reiterates that knowing the causes of educational worry and infection-related concern that teachers encounter in face-to-face sessions during a pandemic. However, the study findings outweighed this concern, the advantage of going back and finally being able to address difficulties in teaching during online classes.

The life lessons learned in the entire experience of transition brought significant changes in the life of the participants as nurse educators. The learning experience that transpired during the transition shows that challenges in the educational system are means to the improvement of teaching. Three themes emerged in the study by Tran et al. (2021) to highlight the lessons that were learned throughout the pandemic which include preparation for in-person classes, the emotional state of faculty, staff, and students; and innovative practices. According to Miyagawa and Perdue (2020), during the transition, educators engage creatively and enthusiastically not only while teaching online but also when doing so with a new perspective on the subject. On the other hand, nurse educators' struggles with distance learning hurt nurse instructors' perception of distance education while their positive experiences had the opposite effect (Eycan and Ulupinar, 2021).

Proposed Faculty Development Activities

The proposed activities to enhance the skills in teaching not only during a pandemic crisis that requires online teaching modality but also for the nurse educators' continued growth and development through various activities identified by themselves indicates the needs for development along the 3 areas as follows: instructional materials development, use of technology and instructional strategies. According to Hainsworth and Keyes(2016), the means of information transmission are instructional materials. Which is important during the delivery of teaching. During the pandemic schools largely continued to be open, so they hurried to move all classes and learning materials online. As a result, academic staff has frequently hurried to transfer learning resources and materials to online learning platforms while also modifying lecture content for streaming and/or home-based recording (Heitz, et al, 2020). The current study recognized the need for skills development in this aspect of teaching. On the other hand, the use of technology seems with equal importance in faculty development. Bisnar (2022) suggested that teachers must be able to keep up with technological changes to properly prepare students in a digital age. Therefore, schools must ensure then that teachers receive consistent, continuous training and skill development that ensures efficacy in teaching in various modes of modalities.

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 13 of 16

Chapter 4
Conclusion and Recommendation

The nurse educator's moderate level of self-efficacy in online teaching allows room for improvement in situations that call for an online teaching modality. It would be advantageous rather than a disadvantage to have an ongoing opportunity to teach online, such as during flexible learning. This investigation centered on nurse educators' transition of teachings from online teaching to flexible and back. The transitions challenged everyone but eventually had gradually adjusted and adapted to changes in teaching modalities. Regardless of the teaching mode, they will transition to, this study shows the benefit of educating and training nurse educators to increase their self-efficacy as teachers whether online or offline. When there is a crisis in the educational system, nurse educators can adjust by having access to programs for faculty development that are tailored to their needs through school initiatives.

References

Allison B. Hall & Jesús Trespalacios (2019) Personalized Professional Learning and Teacher Self-Efficacy for Integrating Technology in K-12 Classrooms, *Journal of Digital Learning in Teacher Education*, 35:4, 221-235, DOI: [10.1080/21532974.2019.1647579](https://doi.org/10.1080/21532974.2019.1647579)

Atout, M., Mohammed, A., Dreidi, M. Khader, I. and Jaghama, M.(2022).Challenges to online education during the time of COVID-19: A focus group study. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1111/nuf.12800>

Baroudi S, Shaya N. Exploring predictors of teachers' self-efficacy for online teaching in the Arab world amid COVID-19. *Educ Inf Technol (Dordr)*. 2022;27(6):8093-8110. doi: 10.1007/s10639-022-10946-4. Epub 2022 Mar 1. PMID: 35250355; PMCID: PMC8886344.

Burns, M. (2016). Ensuring quality online learning for teachers. Retrieved from: <https://www.globalpartnership.org/blog/ensuring-quality-online-learning-teachers>

Caprara, G.V., Barbaranelli C., Steca P., Malone P.S. (2006). Teacher's self-efficacy belief as determinants of job satisfaction and student's academic achievement: a study at the school level. *Journal School of Psychology*.44 473-490.10.1016

Carpena,J.(2022).Going back to face-to-face. from <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/going-back-to-face-to-face-classes/Going-Back-to-Face-to-Face-Classes>

Dewart, G., Corcoran, L., Thirsk, L., & Petrovic, K. (2020). Nursing education in a pandemic: Academic challenges in response to COVID-19. *Nurse education today*, 92, 104471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2020.104471>

Dolighan, T. and Owen,M. (2021). Teacher Efficacy for Online Teaching During the COVID-19 Pandemic A journal of educational research and practice 2021 Vol. 30 (1) 95-116 <https://journals.library.brocku.ca/brocked>

Eycan Ö, and Ulupinar S.(2021). Nurse instructors' perception towards distance education during the pandemic. *Nurse Educ Today*. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2021.105102.

SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 14 of 16

Evans, N. J., Forney, D. S., & Guido-Dibrito, F. (1998). *Student development in college: Theory, research, and practice*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass

Firmansyah, F. and Bandon, A. (2022). Motivating Teachers During the COVID-19 Pandemic. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5885-3749>

Garcia, P. and Cruz, L. (2022). Transitioning to Online and Flexible Modes of Delivery: Challenges and Opportunities During and Beyond the COVID-19 Pandemic in the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://ajodl.oum.edu.my/document/Previous/Volume13.N0.2>

Hainsworth, D. and Keyes, K. (2016). Instructional materials. <https://nursekey.com/instructional-materials>

Hampton, D., Culp-Roche, A., Hensley, A., Wilson, J.L., Otts, J.A., Thaxton-Wiggins, A., Fruh, S.M., & Moser, D.K. (2020). Self-efficacy and Satisfaction With Teaching in Online Courses. *Nurse Educator*, 45, 302 - 306.

Heitz, C., Laboissiere, M., Sanghvi, S., and Sarakatsannis, J. (2020). *Getting the Next Phase of Remote Learning Right in Higher Education*. Available online at: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/public-and-social-sector/our-insights/getting-the-next-phase-of-remote-learning-right-in-higher-education>

Hinton, V. (2020). Facing the Disconnect: College Students and Online Learning. <https://digitalpromise.org/2020/08/18/facing-the-disconnect-college-students-and-online-learning>

Lee, M. and Tsai, C. (2010). Exploring teacher's perceived self-efficacy and technological pedagogical content knowledge with respect to educational use of the worldwide web. *Instructional Science*, 38(1), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11251-008-9075-4>.

Miyagawa, S. and Perdue, M. (2020). A renewed focus on the practice of teaching. <https://www.insidehighered.com>

Moradi, Y., Baghei, A., Reza, F., and Beigloo, H. (2022). Challenges of the sudden shift to asynchronous virtual education in nursing education during the COVID-19 pandemic: A qualitative study. Retrieved from doi: 10.4103/nms.nms_82_21

Müller, C., Mildenerger, T. & Steingruber, D. Learning effectiveness of a flexible learning study programme in a blended learning design: why are some courses more effective than others?. *Int J Educ Technol High Educ* 20, 10 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-022-00379-x>

Pokhrel, S. and Chhetri, R. (2021). A literature review on the impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning. Vol. 8 Issue no. 1. Retrieved from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347631120983481>

Rojas, J.F. (2021). Flexible learning as the new normal. Retrieved from:

SAINT MARY' S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES
UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 15 of 16

<https://businessmirror.com.ph/2021/05/24/flexible-learning-as-the-new-normal/>

Sarkar, S. (2020). A brief history of online education. Retrieved from <https://adamasuniversity.ac.in/a-brief-history-of-online-education>

Schlossberg, N. K., Waters, E. B., & Goodman, J. (1995). *Counseling adults in transition: Linking practice with theory* (2nd ed.). New York: Spring.

Subedi, S., Nayaju, S. Subedi, S., Shah, S., and Shah, J. (2020). Impact of E-learning during COVID-19 Pandemic among Nursing Students and Teachers of Nepal. *International Journal of Science and Healthcare Research* Vol.5; Issue: 3. Retrieved from <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/64126179/IJSHR0012-with-cover-page->

Tran A., Kerkstra R., Gardocki S., and Papuga S. (2021). Lessons Learned: Teaching In-Person During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal in Frontiers in Education*. Vol 6 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/feduc.2021.690646>

Vargas R. and Oros L. (2021) Stress and Burnout in Teachers During Times of Pandemic. *Journal Frontiers in Psychology*. Vol 12. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.756007>

SAINT MARY' S UNIVERSITY

BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER

Document Code	URC-FO-060
Revision	02
Effectivity Date	2022/11/17
Page/s	Page 16 of 16

